

Machine learning discoveries of ABC transporter-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells

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Abstract

Often, in biology, we are faced with the problem of exploring relevant unknown biological hypotheses in the form of myriads of combinations of factors/genes/proteins that might be affecting the pathway under certain conditions. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, many genes were found up and down regulated, individually. A recently developed search engine ranked combinations of ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters-X (X, a particular gene/protein) at 2^{nd} order level after drug administration. These rankings reveal which ABC-X combinations might be working synergistically in CRC. If found true, oncologists can further test the combination of interest in wet lab and determine the mechanism of functioning between the ABC and X. In this research work, we cover combinations of ABC with ubiquitin-conjugating enzymes (UBE2), Interleukin (IL), BCL and Caspase (CASP).

Keywords: ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters, Porcupine inhibitor ETC-1922159, Sensitivity analysis, Colorectal cancer.

1. Introduction

In the unpublished preprint Sinha [1], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Such combinations are of import due to the vast search space in which they exist and the difficulty to find them. The search engine facilitates in prioritizing the combinations as ranked biological hypotheses which the biologists might want to test in wet lab, to know if a synergistic combination is prevalent in a signaling pathway, in a direct or indirect manner. Interested readers are advised to go through unpublished preprints Sinha [1] and Sinha [2] for details regarding the search engine and the discoveries mentioned in there.

^{*}ML dicoveries of ABC transporter synergy in ETC-1922159 treated CRC cells

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¹Aspects of unpublished work were presented in a poster session at (1) the recently concluded first ever Wnt Gordon Conference, from 6-11 August 2017, held in Stowe, VT 05672, USA.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

The issue of combinatorial search problem and a possible solution has been addressed in Sinha [3] and Sinha [2]. The details of the methodology of this manuscript have been explained in great detail in Sinha [3] & its application in Sinha [2]. Readers are requested to go through the same for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159. In order to understand the significance of the solution proposed to the problem of combinatorial search that the biologists face in revealing unknown biological search problem, these works are of importance.

Briefly, from Sinha [2], the pipeline works by computing sensitivity indices for each of these unique combinations and then vectorising these indices to connote and form discriminative feature vector for each combination. Since each combination is unique, the training and the test data are same. In the training data, the combinations are arranged and ranks from 1 to n are assigned. The ranking algorithm then learns the patterns from these combinations/sensitivity index vectors. Next the learned model is used to rank the test data by generating the ranking score for each of the unique combination. Sorting these shuffled scores of test data leads to prioritization of the combinations. Joachims [4] show an example of applying learned model to training data (same as the test data) in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. Note that these combinations are now ranked and give the biologists a chance to narrow down their focus on crucial biological hypotheses in the form of combinations which the biologists might want to test. Analogous to the webpage search engine, where the click of a button for a few key-words leads to a ranked list of web links, the pipeline uses sensitivity indices as an indicator of the strength of the influence of factors or their combinations, as a criteria to rank the combinations.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. ABC transporter related synergies

3.1.1. ABC transporters - UBE2 cross family analysis

Not much is known about the interaction or any possible direct/indirect synergy of ABC transporters and the Ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2 family. In CRC cells treated with ETC-1922159, family members of both were found to be up regulated. The search engine also assigned numerically high valued ranks to a few of 2^{nd} order synergies between the the two. We document here these synergies and show the possible unexplored combinations between the two families. Tables 1 and 2 show the rankings of ABC w.r.t UBE2 and vice versa, respectively.

In table 1 we found **ABC-C3** up regulated w.r.t UBE2-A. This is reflected in the rankings of 2137 (laplace) and 2491 (linear) for ABC-C3 - UBE2-A. **ABC-C5** was up regulated w.r.t UBE2-B. This is reflected in the rankings of 2317 (laplace) and 2266 (rbf) for ABC-C5 - UBE2-B. **ABC-A5/D1/G2** were up regulated w.r.t UBE2-F. These

RANKING ABC FAMILY W.R.T UBE2 FAMILY								
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T UBE2-A				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T UBE2-B				
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
ABC-A5 - UBE2-A	2101	185	382	ABC-A5 - UBE2-B	1223	1193	194	
ABC-B11 - UBE2-A	129	2487	304	ABC-B11 - UBE2-B	125	103	571	
ABC-C3 - UBE2-A	2137	2491	1023	ABC-C3 - UBE2-B	606	791	1411	
ABC-C5 - UBE2-A	1630	490	2408	ABC-C5 - UBE2-B	1515	2317	2266	
ABC-C13 - UBE2-A	742	1604	475	ABC-C13 - UBE2-B	2199	2254	2362	
ABC-D1 - UBE2-A	316	620	596	ABC-D1 - UBE2-B	1082	374	1057	
ABC-G1 - UBE2-A	46	819	533	ABC-G1 - UBE2-B	48	843	551	
ABC-G2 - UBE2-A	398	259	261	ABC-G2 - UBE2-B	189	189	41	
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T UBE2-F				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T UBE2-H				
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
ABC-A5 - UBE2-F	997	2408	1784	ABC-A5 - UBE2-H	1247	2068	2438	
ABC-B11 - UBE2-F	141	1122	578	ABC-B11 - UBE2-H	932	429	409	
ABC-C3 - UBE2-F	931	2420	681	ABC-C3 - UBE2-H	540	1962	563	
ABC-C5 - UBE2-F	628	1373	217	ABC-C5 - UBE2-H	1551	865	1450	
ABC-C13 - UBE2-F	403	2464	1307	ABC-C13 - UBE2-H	1192	2492	2051	
ABC-D1 - UBE2-F	2069	1959	1235	ABC-D1 - UBE2-H	1094	1016	1474	
ABC-G1 - UBE2-F	209	1216	1450	ABC-G1 - UBE2-H	683	173	18	
ABC-G2 - UBE2-F	690	1995	2120	ABC-G2 - UBE2-H	1328	1374	78	
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T UBE2-J1				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T UBE2-Z				
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
ABC-A5 - UBE2-J1	634	222	711	ABC-A5 - UBE2-Z	454	1059	1287	
ABC-B11 - UBE2-J1	1182	1075	403	ABC-B11 - UBE2-Z	134	503	436	
ABC-C3 - UBE2-J1	1232	719	1285	ABC-C3 - UBE2-Z	975	1722	2095	
ABC-C5 - UBE2-J1	964	1342	2373	ABC-C5 - UBE2-Z	2348	845	1859	
ABC-C13 - UBE2-J1	2095	2412	2360	ABC-C13 - UBE2-Z	1157	651	1335	
ABC-D1 - UBE2-J1	542	1198	704	ABC-D1 - UBE2-Z	392	1660	943	
ABC-G1 - UBE2-J1	306	97	122	ABC-G1 - UBE2-Z	545	142	354	
ABC-G2 - UBE2-J1	335	668	591	ABC-G2 - UBE2-Z	747	285	530	

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between ABC w.r.t UBE2 family members.

are reflected in the rankings of 2408 (linear) and 1784 (rbf) for ABC-A5 - UBE2-F, 2069 (linear) and 1959 (rbf) for ABC-D1 - UBE2-F and 1995 (linear) and 2120 (rbf) for ABC-G2 - UBE2-F. **ABC-A5/C13** were up regulated w.r.t UBE2-H. These are reflected in 2068 (linear) and 2438 (rbf) for ABC-A5 - UBE2-H and 2492 (linear) and 2051 (rbf) for ABC-C13 - UBE2-H. **ABC-C13** was up regulated w.r.t UBE2-J1. This is reflected in the rankings of 2095 (laplace), 2412 (linear) and 2360 (rbf). **ABC-C5** was up regulated w.r.t UBE2-Z. This is reflected in rankings of 2348 (laplace) and 1859 (rbf) for ABC-C5 - UBE2-Z.

In table 2 we found **UBE2-A** up regulated w.r.t ABC-C5/G2. This is reflected in the rankings of 2122 (linear) and 2297 (rbf) for ABC-C5 - UBE2-A; and 2048 (laplace) and 1829 (linear) for ABC-G2 - UBE2-A. **UBE2-B** up regulated w.r.t ABC-A5/C3/C13/D1/G2. This is reflected in the rankings of 1846 (laplace) and 2038 (linear) for ABC-A5 - UBE2-B; 1999 (laplace) and 2050 (rbf) for ABC-C3 - UBE2-B; 1863 (linear) and 2496 (rbf) for ABC-C13 - UBE2-B; 2322 (laplace), 1917 (linear) and 2426 (rbf) for ABC-D1 - UBE2-B and 1833 (laplace), 2445 (linear) and 2506 (rbf)

RANKING UBE2 FAMILY W.R.T ABC FAMILY								
RANKING OF UBE2-A W.R.T ABC				RANKING OF UBE2-B W.R.T ABC FAMILY				
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
ABC-A5 - UBE2-A	1037	253	2091	ABC-A5 - UBE2-B	1846	2038	936	
ABC-B11 - UBE2-A	1491	1269	2179	ABC-B11 - UBE2-B	1623	1304	1995	
ABC-C3 - UBE2-A	1726	1906	1390	ABC-C3 - UBE2-B	1999	832	2050	
ABC-C5 - UBE2-A	880	2122	2297	ABC-C5 - UBE2-B	612	2276	1681	
ABC-C13 - UBE2-A	412	234	670	ABC-C13 - UBE2-B	467	1863	2496	
ABC-D1 - UBE2-A	2507	237	1319	ABC-D1 - UBE2-B	2322	1917	2426	
ABC-G1 - UBE2-A	907	2291	1573	ABC-G1 - UBE2-B	1194	1592	1239	
ABC-G2 - UBE2-A	2048	1829	1376	ABC-G2 - UBE2-B	1833	2445	2506	
RANKING OF UBE2-F W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF UBE2-H W.R.T ABC FAMILY				
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
ABC-A5 - UBE2-F	2485	406	66	ABC-A5 - UBE2-H	508	2339	1110	
ABC-B11 - UBE2-F	2003	1203	2422	ABC-B11 - UBE2-H	1950	1770	2461	
ABC-C3 - UBE2-F	2132	2163	861	ABC-C3 - UBE2-H	2439	1972	2305	
ABC-C5 - UBE2-F	406	1651	1838	ABC-C5 - UBE2-H	398	2473	2355	
ABC-C13 - UBE2-F	821	959	1196	ABC-C13 - UBE2-H	2004	2317	1847	
ABC-D1 - UBE2-F	2421	686	2176	ABC-D1 - UBE2-H	164	1641	648	
ABC-G1 - UBE2-F	115	2202	1953	ABC-G1 - UBE2-H	201	1921	2288	
ABC-G2 - UBE2-F	983	883	1012	ABC-G2 - UBE2-H	2063	1631	1354	
RANKING OF UBE2-J1 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF UBE2-Z W.R.T ABC FAMILY				
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf	
ABC-A5 - UBE2-J1	1740	1467	1244	ABC-A5 - UBE2-Z	2336	1710	35	
ABC-B11 - UBE2-J1	1806	991	1935	ABC-B11 - UBE2-Z	521	645	2168	
ABC-C3 - UBE2-J1	2073	2291	631	ABC-C3 - UBE2-Z	1978	1823	1859	
ABC-C5 - UBE2-J1	126	525	1409	ABC-C5 - UBE2-Z	1237	148	1928	
ABC-C13 - UBE2-J1	2329	2153	1951	ABC-C13 - UBE2-Z	1185	137	2475	
ABC-D1 - UBE2-J1	2263	1886	2249	ABC-D1 - UBE2-Z	2292	21	2381	
ABC-G1 - UBE2-J1	1262	2418	2277	ABC-G1 - UBE2-Z	426	2515	1858	
ABC-G2 - UBE2-J1	1558	2408	1304	ABC-G2 - UBE2-Z	2270	2080	2448	

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between UBE2 w.r.t ABC family members.

for ABC-G2 - UBE2-B. **UBE2-F** was found up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11/C3/D1/G1. These were reflected in 2003 (laplace) and 2422 (rbf) for ABC-B11 - UBE2-F; 2132 (laplace) and 2163 (linear) for ABC-C3 - UBE2-F; 2421 (laplace) and 2176 (rbf) for ABC-D1 - UBE2-F; and 2202 (laplace) and 1953 (rbf) for ABC-G1 - UBE2-F. **UBE2-H** was found to be up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11/C3/C5/C13/G1. These are reflected in rankings of 1950 (laplace), 1770 (linear) and 2461 (rbf) for ABC-B11 - UBE2-H; 2439 (laplace), 1972 (linear) and 2305 (rbf) for ABC-C3 - UBE2-H; 2473 (linear) and 2355 (rbf) for ABC-C5 - UBE2-H; 2004 (laplace), 2317 (linear) and 1847 (rbf) for ABC-C13 - UBE2-H; and 1921 (linear) and 2288 (rbf) for ABC-G1 - UBE2-H; **UBE2-J1** was found to be up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11/C3/C13/D1/G1/G2; 1806 (laplace) and 1935 (rbf) for ABC-B11 - UBE2-J1; 2073 (laplace) and 2291 (linear) for ABC-C3 - UBE2-J1; 2329 (laplace), 2153 (linear) and 1951 (rbf) for ABC-C13 - UBE2-J1; 2263 (laplace), 1886 (linear) and 2249 (rbf) for ABC-D1 - UBE2-J1; and 2418 (linear) and 2277 (rbf) for ABC-G1 - UBE2-J1; Finally, **UBE2-Z** was found up regulated w.r.t ABC-C3/D1/G1/G2. These are reflected in rankings of 1978 (laplace), 1823 (linear)

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

ABC w.r.t UBE2	
ABC-C3	UBE2-A
ABC-C5	UBE2-B
ABC-A5/D1/G2	UBE2-F
ABC-A5/C13	UBE2-H
ABC-C13	UBE2-J1
ABC-C5	UBE2-Z
UBE2 w.r.t ABC	
UBE2-A	ABC-C5/G2
UBE2-B	ABC-A5/C3/C13/D1/G2
UBE2-F	ABC-B11/C3/D1/G1
UBE2-H	ABC-B11/C3/C5/C13/G1
UBE2-J1	ABC-B11/C3/C13/D1/G1/G2
UBE2-Z	ABC-C3/D1/G1/G2

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between ABC and UBE2.

and 1859 (rbf) for ABC-C3 - UBE2-Z; 2292 (laplace) and 2381 (linear) for ABC-D1 - UBE2-Z; 2515 (linear) and 1858 (rbf) for ABC-G1 - UBE2-Z; 2270 (laplace), 2080 (linear) and 2448 (rbf) for ABC-G2 - UBE2-Z.

Table 3 shows the derived influences which can be represented graphically, with the following influences -

85 • ABC w.r.t UBE2 with ABC-C3 < - UBE2-A; ABC-C5 < - UBE2-B; ABC-A5/D1/G2 < - UBE2-F; ABC-A5/C13 < - UBE2-H; ABC-C13 < - UBE2-J1; ABC-C5 < - UBE2-Z; and

• UBE2 w.r.t ABC with UBE2-A < - ABC-C5/G2; UBE2-B < - ABC-A5/C3/C13/D1/G2; UBE2-F < - ABC-B11/C3/D1/G1; UBE2-H < - ABC-B11/C3/C5/C13/G1; UBE2-J1 < - ABC-B11/C3/C13/D1/G1/G2;

90 UBE2-Z < - ABC-C3/D1/G1/G2.

3.1.2. ABC transporters intra cross family analysis

A range of ABC transporters were found to be up regulated in CRC cells after ETC-1922159 treatment. We checked the rankings of the ABC transporters within the ABC family and found multiple synergistic upregulation at 2nd order level that were ranked appropriately. Table 4 shows intra family rankings of ABC members among themselves. We found **ABC-C13** upregulated w.r.t ABC-A5. These were reflected in rankings of 1943 (linear) and 2151 (rbf); **ABC-C5/C13/G1** were up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11. These are reflected in rankings of 2226 (laplace) and 2241 (rbf) for ABC-C5 - ABC-B11; 1971 (laplace) and 2150 (rbf) for ABC-C13 - ABC-B11 and 1957 (laplace) and 1920 (linear) for ABC-G1 - ABC-B11; **ABC-C3/C13** were found to be up regulated w.r.t ABC-C5. These are reflected in 2084 (laplace), 2274 (linear) and 1758 (rbf) for ABC-C3 - ABC-C5 and 2476 (linear) and 2446 (rbf) for ABC-C13 - ABC-C5. **ABC-C5/C13** were found to be up regulated w.r.t ABC-D1. 2423 (laplace) and 2388 (rbf) for ABC-C5 - ABC-D1 and 2383 (laplace) and 2029 (linear) for ABC-C13 - ABC-D1. **ABC-A5** was found to be up regulated w.r.t ABC-G1. This is reflected in rankings of 2488 (laplace) and 1776 (linear) for ABC-A5 - ABC-G1. **ABC-A5** was found to be up regulated w.r.t ABC-G2 also. This is reflected in rankings of 2284 (laplace), 1904 (linear) and 1829 (rbf) for ABC-A5 - ABC-G2.

Table 5 shows the derived influences which can be represented graphically, with the following influences - • ABC intra family with ABC-C13 < - ABC-A5; ABC-C5/C13/G1 < - ABC-B11; ABC-C3/C13 < - ABC-C5; ABC-C5/C13 < - ABC-D1; ABC-A5 < - ABC-G1; ABC-C5 < - ABC-G2.

RANKING ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC FAMILY							
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-A5				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-B11			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABC-B11 - ABC-A5	733	471	26	ABC-A5 - ABC-B11	1148	1443	1782
ABC-C3 - ABC-A5	111	493	2264	ABC-C3 - ABC-B11	845	527	1257
ABC-C5 - ABC-A5	1717	519	1921	ABC-C5 - ABC-B11	2226	1644	2241
ABC-C13 - ABC-A5	1243	1943	2151	ABC-C13 - ABC-B11	1971	609	2150
ABC-D1 - ABC-A5	1262	2387	1573	ABC-D1 - ABC-B11	891	217	854
ABC-G1 - ABC-A5	657	991	533	ABC-G1 - ABC-B11	1957	1920	669
ABC-G2 - ABC-A5	587	397	104	ABC-G2 - ABC-B11	685	1978	226
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-C3				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-C5			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABC-A5 - ABC-C3	163	861	1672	ABC-A5 - ABC-C5	2086	411	1243
ABC-B11 - ABC-C3	410	613	1501	ABC-B11 - ABC-C5	2398	272	464
ABC-C5 - ABC-C3	1591	2435	927	ABC-C3 - ABC-C5	2084	2274	1758
ABC-C13 - ABC-C3	405	880	1282	ABC-C13 - ABC-C5	226	2476	2446
ABC-D1 - ABC-C3	18	1145	2187	ABC-D1 - ABC-C5	2010	891	1257
ABC-G1 - ABC-C3	1858	173	842	ABC-G1 - ABC-C5	2402	894	741
ABC-G2 - ABC-C3	1462	275	1373	ABC-G2 - ABC-C5	2463	736	661
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-C13				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-D1			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABC-A5 - ABC-C13	2251	1219	1614	ABC-A5 - ABC-D1	163	1068	291
ABC-B11 - ABC-C13	1106	56	1171	ABC-B11 - ABC-D1	1273	130	1655
ABC-C3 - ABC-C13	2279	1431	365	ABC-C3 - ABC-D1	568	251	149
ABC-C5 - ABC-C13	1537	2178	690	ABC-C5 - ABC-D1	2423	538	2388
ABC-D1 - ABC-C13	2370	171	362	ABC-C13 - ABC-D1	2383	2029	425
ABC-G1 - ABC-C13	833	1544	1343	ABC-G1 - ABC-D1	1462	1175	827
ABC-G2 - ABC-C13	329	1323	1755	ABC-G2 - ABC-D1	467	670	2491
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-G1				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T ABC-G2			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABC-A5 - ABC-G1	2488	1776	1078	ABC-A5 - ABC-G2	1011	1640	1705
ABC-B11 - ABC-G1	2312	253	52	ABC-B11 - ABC-G2	988	481	1849
ABC-C3 - ABC-G1	273	1415	1139	ABC-C3 - ABC-G2	1102	1082	1563
ABC-C5 - ABC-G1	220	1988	437	ABC-C5 - ABC-G2	2284	1904	1829
ABC-C13 - ABC-G1	2389	427	1125	ABC-C13 - ABC-G2	929	1238	222
ABC-D1 - ABC-G1	1836	485	597	ABC-D1 - ABC-G2	814	995	1152
ABC-G2 - ABC-G1	2506	692	1143	ABC-G1 - ABC-G2	596	460	848

Table 4: 2nd order interaction ranking between ABC family members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

ABC intra family

ABC-C13	ABC-A5
ABC-C5/C13/G1	ABC-B11
ABC-C3/C13	ABC-C5
ABC-C5/C13	ABC-D1
ABC-A5	ABC-G1
ABC-C5	ABC-G2

Table 5: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between ABC family members.

3.1.3. Interleukin - ABC transporters cross family analysis

Zhou et al. [5] have observed that the ABCA1 contributes to the secretion of interleukin 1β from macrophages. Haskó et al. [6] show that inhibitors of ABC transporters suppress interleukin-12 p40 production and major histocompatibility complex II up-regulation in macrophages. Park et al. [7] conclude that anti-cancer drug-induced IL-8 secretion increased the expression of ABC transporters and SP cells, promoting the growth of HCC in vitro. Marty et al. [8] show that ABC1 is required for the release of interleukin- 1β by P2X7-stimulated and lipopolysaccharide-primed mouse Schwann cells. Lottaz et al. [9] observe that inhibition of ABC transporter downregulates interleukin- 1β -mediated autocrine activation of human dermal fibroblasts. These findings and many more indicate the synergy between IL family and ABC transporters. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, some of the members of both families were up regulated. Given the studied synergies, our search engine found multiple combinations which were ranked with high numerical values, thus indicating possible dual combinatorial role. Tables 6 and 7, each show rankings of ABC transporters w.r.t IL family on the left half and vice versa on the right half.

On the left half we found **IL-17REL** up regulated w.r.t ABCA5. This is reflected in the rankings of 2405 (linear) and 2202 (rbf) for IL17REL - ABCA5. **IL-2RG/6ST/15/15RA** up regulated w.r.t ABCB11. This is reflected in the rankings of 2182 (laplace), 2102 (linear) and 550 (rbf) for IL2RG - ABCB11; 1793 (laplace), 2140 (linear) and 1938 (rbf) for IL6ST - ABCB11; 2438 (laplace) and 2512 (linear) for IL15 - ABCB11; and 2271 (laplace) and 1784 (rbf) for IL15RA - ABCB11. **IL-8/15RA** up regulated w.r.t ABCC3. This is reflected in the rankings of 1767 (laplace) and 2419 (rbf) for IL8 - ABCC3 and 2403 (linear) and 1795 (rbf) for IL15RA - ABCC3. **IL-15RA/17REL** up regulated w.r.t ABCC5. These are reflected in rankings of 2255 (linear) and 1861 (rbf) for IL15RA - ABCC5 and 2462 (linear) and 2509 (rbf) for IL17REL - ABCC5. **IL-15RA/17REL** were up regulated w.r.t ABCC13. These are reflected in 2248 (laplace), 1955 (linear) and 2456 (rbf) for IL15RA - ABCC13 and 2339 (laplace) and 2137 (linear) for IL17REL - ABCC13. **IL-1A/1RAP/8/15RA** were up regulated w.r.t ABCD1. These are reflected in rankings of 1932 (laplace) and 2203 (rbf) for IL1A - ABCD1; 2508 (laplace), 2006 (linear) and 1907 (rbf) for IL1RAP - ABCD1; 2010 (laplace), 2315 (linear) and 1814 (rbf) for IL8 - ABCD1; and 2097 (laplace) and 1765 (linear) for IL15RA - ABCD1. **IL-1RAP** was up regulated w.r.t ABCG1. This was reflected in rankings of 2205 (linear) and 2339 (rbf) for IL1RAP - ABCG1. **IL-1RAP/15RA** were up regulated w.r.t ABCG2. These were reflected in rankings of 2184 (laplace) and 2167 (linear) for IL1RAP - ABCG2 and 1910 (laplace), 2428 (linear) and 1921 (rbf) for IL15RA - ABCG2.

On the right half we found **ABCA5** up regulated w.r.t IL-1B/1RAP/10RB. These are reflected in the rankings of 2069 (laplace) and 2301 (rbf) for IL1B - ABCA5; 1763 (laplace) and 2345 (rbf) for IL1RAP - ABCA5; and 2230 (laplace), 2184 (linear) and 2240 (rbf) for IL10RB - ABCA5; **ABCB11** was up regulated w.r.t IL-10RB. This is reflected in the rankings of 2101 (laplace) and 2419 (linear) for IL10RB - ABCB11. **ABCC3** was up regulated w.r.t IL-1A/17REL. This is reflected in the rankings of 1798 (linear) and 2459 (rbf) for IL1A - ABCC3 and 2089 (laplace) and 2388 (linear) for IL17REL - ABCC3. **ABCC5** was up regulated w.r.t IL-1A/1RAP/15/17C. This are

reflected in the rankings of 2217 (laplace) and 2022 (linear) for IL1A - ABCC5; 1982 (laplace), 1892 (linear) and 2296 (rbf) for IL1RAP - ABCC5; 1947 (laplace) and 1991 (linear) for IL15 - ABCC5 and 1836 (laplace) and 1802 (rbf) for IL17C - ABCC5. **ABCC13** was up regulated w.r.t IL-1RAP/15RA. This are reflected in the rankings of 2136 (laplace) and 2392 (linear) for IL1RAP - ABCC13 and 2397 (laplace) and 2485 (linear) for IL15RA - ABCC13; **ABCD1** was up regulated w.r.t IL-8/10RB. This are reflected in the rankings of 2501 (laplace) and 2154 (linear) for IL8 - ABCD1 and 1795 (laplace) and 2325 (rbf) for IL10RB - ABCD1. **ABCG2** was up regulated w.r.t IL-10RB. This is reflected in the rankings of 2144 (laplace), 2335 (linear) and 2434 (rbf) for IL10RB - ABCG2.

Table 8 shows the derived influences which can be represented graphically, with the following influences - ● ABC w.r.t IL with IL-1B/1RAP/10RB \rightarrow ABCA5; IL-10RB \rightarrow ABCB11; IL-1A/17REL \rightarrow ABCC3; IL-1A/1RAP/15/17C \rightarrow ABCC5; IL-1RAP/15RA \rightarrow ABCC13; IL-8/10RB \rightarrow ABCD1 and IL-10RB \rightarrow ABCG2; ● IL w.r.t ABC with IL-17REL \leftarrow ABCA5; IL-2RG/6ST/15/15RA \leftarrow ABCB11; IL-8/15RA \leftarrow ABCC3; IL-15RA/17REL \leftarrow ABCC5; IL-15RA/17REL \leftarrow ABCC13; IL-1A/1RAP/8/15RA \leftarrow ABCD1; IL-1RAP \leftarrow ABCG1 and IL-1RAP/15RA \leftarrow ABCG2;

RANKING ABC FAMILY VS IL FAMILY

RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCA5				RANKING OF ABCA5 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCA5	705	95	11	IL1A - ABCA5	677	2069	871
IL1B - ABCA5	240	35	353	IL1B - ABCA5	2069	790	2301
IL1RAP - ABCA5	1515	2354	514	IL1RAP - ABCA5	1763	335	2345
IL1RN - ABCA5	771	1093	1417	IL1RN - ABCA5	892	2252	1482
IL2RG - ABCA5	500	246	173	IL2RG - ABCA5	993	750	1745
IL6ST - ABCA5	2464	1564	1365	IL6ST - ABCA5	155	266	1386
IL8 - ABCA5	1676	1568	1111	IL8 - ABCA5	104	1261	946
IL10RB - ABCA5	492	146	643	IL10RB - ABCA5	2230	2184	2240
IL15 - ABCA5	638	1169	65	IL15 - ABCA5	661	169	711
IL15RA - ABCA5	2151	1672	740	IL15RA - ABCA5	706	1300	2031
IL17C - ABCA5	680	197	164	IL17C - ABCA5	615	575	1518
IL17REL - ABCA5	1014	2405	2202	IL17REL - ABCA5	212	1024	146
RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCB11				RANKING OF ABCB11 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCB11	1962	465	648	IL1A - ABCB11	551	140	385
IL1B - ABCB11	1778	851	438	IL1B - ABCB11	255	428	208
IL1RAP - ABCB11	1427	1704	1318	IL1RAP - ABCB11	1681	878	1709
IL1RN - ABCB11	1832	539	297	IL1RN - ABCB11	342	1912	779
IL2RG - ABCB11	2182	2102	550	IL2RG - ABCB11	814	67	584
IL6ST - ABCB11	1793	2140	1938	IL6ST - ABCB11	1347	1504	385
IL8 - ABCB11	1607	2441	1028	IL8 - ABCB11	349	846	1786
IL10RB - ABCB11	341	1119	449	IL10RB - ABCB11	2101	2419	1352
IL15 - ABCB11	2438	2512	576	IL15 - ABCB11	344	224	256
IL15RA - ABCB11	2271	1288	1784	IL15RA - ABCB11	1052	48	719
IL17C - ABCB11	1262	69	706	IL17C - ABCB11	653	316	437
IL17REL - ABCB11	50	305	783	IL17REL - ABCB11	1004	736	896
RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCC3				RANKING OF ABCC3 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCC3	1860	758	1538	IL1A - ABCC3	1343	1798	2459
IL1B - ABCC3	1764	749	896	IL1B - ABCC3	1647	1369	569
IL1RAP - ABCC3	1514	2294	1989	IL1RAP - ABCC3	2074	1377	303
IL1RN - ABCC3	647	607	1252	IL1RN - ABCC3	1366	975	1354
IL2RG - ABCC3	990	444	40	IL2RG - ABCC3	1229	379	844
IL6ST - ABCC3	98	1589	339	IL6ST - ABCC3	970	712	1342
IL8 - ABCC3	1767	1046	2419	IL8 - ABCC3	937	1033	430
IL10RB - ABCC3	1354	78	359	IL10RB - ABCC3	1609	29	1830
IL15 - ABCC3	1580	602	1560	IL15 - ABCC3	1087	1191	1084
IL15RA - ABCC3	189	2403	1795	IL15RA - ABCC3	2153	163	1324
IL17C - ABCC3	1587	778	2425	IL17C - ABCC3	466	631	2237
IL17REL - ABCC3	1135	403	54	IL17REL - ABCC3	2089	2388	1618
RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCC5				RANKING OF ABCC5 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCC5	2004	681	60	IL1A - ABCC5	2217	2022	1512
IL1B - ABCC5	1948	112	251	IL1B - ABCC5	1223	2137	942
IL1RAP - ABCC5	1038	355	2023	IL1RAP - ABCC5	1982	1892	2296
IL1RN - ABCC5	709	430	1087	IL1RN - ABCC5	1668	816	2142
IL2RG - ABCC5	1421	264	601	IL2RG - ABCC5	500	2018	1691
IL6ST - ABCC5	1569	2010	845	IL6ST - ABCC5	754	2326	874
IL8 - ABCC5	1869	143	1589	IL8 - ABCC5	855	1211	2434
IL10RB - ABCC5	1162	70	434	IL10RB - ABCC5	1337	736	958
IL15 - ABCC5	1262	147	389	IL15 - ABCC5	1947	1991	1584
IL15RA - ABCC5	1083	2255	1861	IL15RA - ABCC5	2457	1444	534
IL17C - ABCC5	2447	96	116	IL17C - ABCC5	1836	845	1802
IL17REL - ABCC5	54	2462	2509	IL17REL - ABCC5	1247	2149	1031

Table 6: 2nd order interaction ranking between ABC and IL family members.

RANKING ABC FAMILY VS IL FAMILY

RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCC13				RANKING OF ABCC13 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCC13	512	135	1207	IL1A - ABCC13	464	352	201
IL1B - ABCC13	152	103	1553	IL1B - ABCC13	635	974	60
IL1RAP - ABCC13	1092	502	2442	IL1RAP - ABCC13	2136	2392	33
IL1RN - ABCC13	1753	559	323	IL1RN - ABCC13	114	1016	1839
IL2RG - ABCC13	2064	674	1076	IL2RG - ABCC13	807	1079	938
IL6ST - ABCC13	332	1416	2112	IL6ST - ABCC13	119	1098	2323
IL8 - ABCC13	551	1200	1680	IL8 - ABCC13	592	984	907
IL10RB - ABCC13	631	621	561	IL10RB - ABCC13	2011	1272	1297
IL15 - ABCC13	502	296	373	IL15 - ABCC13	612	968	170
IL15RA - ABCC13	2248	1955	2456	IL15RA - ABCC13	2397	2485	790
IL17C - ABCC13	25	140	123	IL17C - ABCC13	924	308	711
IL17REL - ABCC13	2339	2137	1497	IL17REL - ABCC13	462	376	461
RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCC5				RANKING OF ABCC5 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCD1	1932	30	2203	IL1A - ABCD1	530	2046	1196
IL1B - ABCD1	569	109	1778	IL1B - ABCD1	1400	605	453
IL1RAP - ABCD1	2508	2006	1907	IL1RAP - ABCD1	399	840	1548
IL1RN - ABCD1	606	2003	789	IL1RN - ABCD1	551	2025	60
IL2RG - ABCD1	1064	284	2374	IL2RG - ABCD1	311	1233	1322
IL6ST - ABCD1	1347	1237	1220	IL6ST - ABCD1	1581	507	612
IL8 - ABCD1	2010	2315	1814	IL8 - ABCD1	2501	2154	539
IL10RB - ABCD1	631	825	85	IL10RB - ABCD1	1795	1028	2325
IL15 - ABCD1	890	325	1578	IL15 - ABCD1	1795	302	1258
IL15RA - ABCD1	2097	1765	1629	IL15RA - ABCD1	580	1240	2342
IL17C - ABCD1	1372	56	2509	IL17C - ABCD1	687	1753	851
IL17REL - ABCD1	5	2388	237	IL17REL - ABCD1	1423	642	2164
RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCG1				RANKING OF ABCG1 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCG1	724	67	80	IL1A - ABCG1	699	824	600
IL1B - ABCG1	938	178	533	IL1B - ABCG1	70	783	81
IL1RAP - ABCG1	1263	2205	2339	IL1RAP - ABCG1	2298	394	612
IL1RN - ABCG1	1240	688	1396	IL1RN - ABCG1	2465	834	1051
IL2RG - ABCG1	1396	7	112	IL2RG - ABCG1	587	24	21
IL6ST - ABCG1	357	845	520	IL6ST - ABCG1	1723	1345	177
IL8 - ABCG1	977	1835	1099	IL8 - ABCG1	1730	1748	382
IL10RB - ABCG1	2244	349	840	IL10RB - ABCG1	167	1315	61
IL15 - ABCG1	1960	613	1279	IL15 - ABCG1	2212	734	326
IL15RA - ABCG1	785	651	2191	IL15RA - ABCG1	1195	862	1876
IL17C - ABCG1	2516	486	51	IL17C - ABCG1	80	95	177
IL17REL - ABCG1	2229	732	150	IL17REL - ABCG1	1579	1025	452
RANKING OF IL FAMILY W.R.T ABCG2				RANKING OF ABCG2 FAMILY W.R.T IL			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
IL1A - ABCG2	745	716	1299	IL1A - ABCG2	238	89	659
IL1B - ABCG2	354	232	668	IL1B - ABCG2	31	197	439
IL1RAP - ABCG2	2184	2167	1384	IL1RAP - ABCG2	1314	253	2434
IL1RN - ABCG2	783	228	11	IL1RN - ABCG2	552	1692	827
IL2RG - ABCG2	444	463	1024	IL2RG - ABCG2	261	87	1275
IL6ST - ABCG2	1647	1827	55	IL6ST - ABCG2	1792	1477	1222
IL8 - ABCG2	2212	1362	563	IL8 - ABCG2	448	441	1423
IL10RB - ABCG2	31	80	667	IL10RB - ABCG2	2144	2335	2434
IL15 - ABCG2	76	312	187	IL15 - ABCG2	247	590	832
IL15RA - ABCG2	1910	2428	1921	IL15RA - ABCG2	1116	1005	1059
IL17C - ABCG2	649	692	61	IL17C - ABCG2	784	462	775
IL17REL - ABCG2	883	1435	35	IL17REL - ABCG2	852	1606	1597

Table 7: 2nd order interaction ranking between ABC and IL family members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

ABC w.r.t IL

IL-1B/1RAP/10RB	ABCA5
IL-10RB	ABCB11
IL-1A/17REL	ABCC3
IL-1A/1RAP/15/17C	ABCC5
IL-1RAP/15RA	ABCC13
IL-8/10RB	ABCD1
IL-10RB	ABCG2

IL w.r.t ABC

IL-17REL	ABCA5
IL-2RG/6ST/15/15RA	ABCB11
IL-8/15RA	ABCC3
IL-15RA/17REL	ABCC5
IL-15RA/17REL	ABCC13
IL-1A/1RAP/8/15RA	ABCD1
IL-1RAP	ABCG1
IL-1RAP/15RA	ABCG2

Table 8: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between ABC and IL family members.

3.1.4. BCL - ABC transporters cross family analysis

Ruzickova et al. [10] show clinically relevant interactions of anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 protein inhibitors with ABC transporters. Alla et al. [11] observe that E2F1 confers anticancer drug resistance by targeting ABC transporter family members and Bcl-2 via the p73/DNp73-miR-205 circuitry. Yasui et al. [12] show a range of ABC family members along with BCL member to be overexpressed while studying the alteration in copy numbers of genes as a mechanism for acquired drug resistance. These point to the possible synergistic workings of BCL with ABC. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these were found to be up regulated. The search engine pointed to some of these 2nd order combinations and allotted rankings of high numerical value, thus indicating possible synergy. Table 9 and 10 show rankings of BCL family w.r.t ABC members on the left half and vice versa on the right half.

On the left half we found **BCL2L1** up regulated w.r.t ABCC5. This is reflected in the rankings of 2239 (laplace) and 1845 (linear). **BCL2L2** was up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11/C5/C13/D1. These are reflected in the rankings of 2097 (laplace) and 2311 (rbf) for ABCB11 - BCL2L2; 2195 (laplace), 2359 (linear) and 2322 (rbf) for ABCC5 - BCL2L2; 2438 (laplace) and 2494 (linear) for ABCC13 - BCL2L2 and 2477 (laplace) and 2156 (rbf) for ABCD1 - BCL2L2. **BCL2L13** was up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11/C5/C13/D1/G1. These are reflected in the rankings of 2505 (laplace) and 1855 (rbf) for ABCB11 - BCL2L13; 1835 (linear) and 2178 (rbf) for ABCC5 - BCL2L13; 2484 (laplace), 2184 (linear) and 2410 (rbf) for ABCC13 - BCL2L13; 2472 (laplace) and 2201 (rbf) for ABCD1 - BCL2L13 and 2276 (linear) and 2095 (rbf) for ABCG1 - BCL2L13. **BCL3** was up regulated w.r.t ABC-D1/G1. These are reflected in the rankings of 2194 (linear) and 2106 (rbf) for ABCD1 - BCL3 and 2014 (laplace) and 2253 (rbf) for ABCG1 - BCL3. **BCL6** was up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11. These are reflected in the rankings of 2010 (linear) and 2350 (rbf) for ABC-B11 - BCL6. **BCL10** was up regulated w.r.t ABC-B11. These are reflected in the rankings of 2234 (laplace) and 2382 (rbf) for ABC-B11 - BCL10.

On the right half we found **ABCC3** up regulated w.r.t BCL2L1. This is reflected in the rankings of 2085 (laplace) and 2309 (linear) for ABCC3 - BCL2L1. **ABC-C5/C13** were up regulated w.r.t BCL2L13. These was reflected in the rankings of 1975 (laplace) and 2421 (linear) for ABCC5 - BCL2L13; and 1894 (laplace), 2335 (linear) and 2475 (rbf) for ABCC13 - BCL2L13. **ABC-C3** was up regulated w.r.t BCL3. This is reflected in the rankings of 1782 (linear) and 2186 (rbf) for ABCC3 - BCL3. **ABC-C5/C13** were up regulated w.r.t BCL6. This is reflected in the rankings of 1841 (linear) and 2389 (rbf) for ABCC5 - BCL6 and 2172 (laplace) and 2456 (linear) for ABCC13 - BCL6. **ABC-C5/C13/D1** were up regulated w.r.t BCL9L. This is reflected in the rankings of 1775 (laplace) and 2073 (rbf) for ABCC5 - BCL9L; 2475 (linear) and 2325 (rbf) for ABCC13 - BCL9L and 2440 (linear) and 2411 (rbf) for ABCD1 - BCL9L; **ABC-A5/C5/C13/D1** were up regulated w.r.t BCL10. These were reflected in the rankings of 1753 (laplace) and 2312 (rbf) for ABCA5 - BCL10; 1775 (laplace) and 2073 (rbf) for ABCC5 - BCL10; 2475 (linear) and 2325 (rbf) for ABCC13 - BCL10 and 2440 (linear) and 2411 (rbf) for ABCD1 - BCL10.

Table 11 shows the derived influences which can be represented graphically, with the following influences - • BCL w.r.t ABC with ABC-C5 – > BCL2L1; ABC-B11/C5/C13/D1

RANKING BCL FAMILY VS ABC FAMILY

RANKING OF BCL2L1 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T BCL2L1			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABCA5 - BCL2L1	18	560	1715	ABCA5 - BCL2L1	1522	220	1818
ABCB11 - BCL2L1	1124	2418	552	ABCB11 - BCL2L1	2002	234	10
ABCC3 - BCL2L1	564	394	64	ABCC3 - BCL2L1	2085	2309	929
ABCC5 - BCL2L1	2239	1845	823	ABCC5 - BCL2L1	599	847	1282
ABCC13 - BCL2L1	805	1590	2407	ABCC13 - BCL2L1	744	616	614
ABCD1 - BCL2L1	356	202	930	ABCD1 - BCL2L1	839	352	195
ABCG1 - BCL2L1	793	2005	885	ABCG1 - BCL2L1	1249	265	1165
ABCG2 - BCL2L1	199	99	906	ABCG2 - BCL2L1	401	620	277
RANKING OF BCL2L2 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T BCL2L2			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABCA5 - BCL2L2	1476	324	1792	ABCA5 - BCL2L2	174	482	501
ABCB11 - BCL2L2	2097	1311	2311	ABCB11 - BCL2L2	148	380	1204
ABCC3 - BCL2L2	1091	1569	259	ABCC3 - BCL2L2	890	949	1398
ABCC5 - BCL2L2	2195	2359	2322	ABCC5 - BCL2L2	765	1875	736
ABCC13 - BCL2L2	2438	2494	898	ABCC13 - BCL2L2	2271	1436	1665
ABCD1 - BCL2L2	2477	831	2156	ABCD1 - BCL2L2	1432	1291	64
ABCG1 - BCL2L2	352	1653	2234	ABCG1 - BCL2L2	406	1206	966
ABCG2 - BCL2L2	1515	2409	1496	ABCG2 - BCL2L2	404	314	55
RANKING OF BCL2L13 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T BCL2L13			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABCA5 - BCL2L13	1398	202	2292	ABCA5 - BCL2L13	655	951	1380
ABCB11 - BCL2L13	2505	261	1855	ABCB11 - BCL2L13	1579	53	224
ABCC3 - BCL2L13	1642	1769	1334	ABCC3 - BCL2L13	265	588	459
ABCC5 - BCL2L13	1427	1835	2178	ABCC5 - BCL2L13	1975	2421	927
ABCC13 - BCL2L13	2484	2184	2410	ABCC13 - BCL2L13	1894	2335	2475
ABCD1 - BCL2L13	2472	1579	2201	ABCD1 - BCL2L13	912	511	1041
ABCG1 - BCL2L13	3	2276	2095	ABCG1 - BCL2L13	957	649	488
ABCG2 - BCL2L13	2172	1723	1502	ABCG2 - BCL2L13	2142	392	1206
RANKING OF BCL3 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T BCL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABCA5 - BCL3	940	45	777	ABCA5 - BCL3	960	1354	2477
ABCB11 - BCL3	260	1002	483	ABCB11 - BCL3	731	1483	2028
ABCC3 - BCL3	2101	214	304	ABCC3 - BCL3	1782	2186	1251
ABCC5 - BCL3	1155	775	1176	ABCC5 - BCL3	2192	957	280
ABCC13 - BCL3	270	1116	1619	ABCC13 - BCL3	1725	1407	1747
ABCD1 - BCL3	759	2194	2106	ABCD1 - BCL3	836	811	1359
ABCG1 - BCL3	2014	1559	2253	ABCG1 - BCL3	550	247	247
ABCG2 - BCL3	480	465	1949	ABCG2 - BCL3	792	798	1418

Table 9: 2nd order interaction ranking between BCL and ABC family members.

– > BCL2L2; ABC-B11/C5/C13/D1/G1 – > BCL2L13; ABC-D1/G1 – > BCL3; ABC-B11 – > BCL6; ABC-B11 – > BCL10; and • ABC w.r.t BCL with ABC-C3 < – BCL2L1; ABC-C5/C13 < – BCL2L13; ABC-C3 < – BCL3; ABC-C5/C13 < – BCL6; ABC-C5/C13/D1 < – BCL9L; ABC-A5/C5/C13/D1 < – BCL10.

RANKING BCL FAMILY VS ABC FAMILY

RANKING OF BCL6 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T BCL6			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABCA5 - BCL6	2045	557	1384	ABCA5 - BCL6	211	283	1615
ABCB11 - BCL6	1611	2010	2350	ABCB11 - BCL6	841	427	2320
ABCC3 - BCL6	1895	983	958	ABCC3 - BCL6	1084	570	594
ABCC5 - BCL6	615	597	567	ABCC5 - BCL6	1370	1841	2389
ABCC13 - BCL6	1097	2431	1731	ABCC13 - BCL6	2172	2456	1063
ABCD1 - BCL6	1446	1139	1953	ABCD1 - BCL6	1097	1297	827
ABCG1 - BCL6	1462	1688	1918	ABCG1 - BCL6	192	27	1111
ABCG2 - BCL6	947	1503	978	ABCG2 - BCL6	129	745	719
RANKING OF BCL9L W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T BCL9L			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABCA5 - BCL9L	67	1008	94	ABCA5 - BCL9L	1753	1167	2312
ABCB11 - BCL9L	1989	158	1705	ABCB11 - BCL9L	1033	494	48
ABCC3 - BCL9L	1307	2249	1357	ABCC3 - BCL9L	457	2296	971
ABCC5 - BCL9L	1694	432	477	ABCC5 - BCL9L	1775	1551	2073
ABCC13 - BCL9L	1724	1410	862	ABCC13 - BCL9L	110	2475	2325
ABCD1 - BCL9L	1366	2344	1666	ABCD1 - BCL9L	1016	2440	2411
ABCG1 - BCL9L	1248	1680	536	ABCG1 - BCL9L	1146	676	16
ABCG2 - BCL9L	2451	1119	224	ABCG2 - BCL9L	1263	1421	218
RANKING OF BCL10 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T BCL10			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ABCA5 - BCL10	687	176	808	ABCA5 - BCL10	1753	1167	2312
ABCB11 - BCL10	2234	2382	322	ABCB11 - BCL10	1033	494	48
ABCC3 - BCL10	589	379	492	ABCC3 - BCL10	457	2296	971
ABCC5 - BCL10	1489	397	1643	ABCC5 - BCL10	1775	1551	2073
ABCC13 - BCL10	956	538	1491	ABCC13 - BCL10	110	2475	2325
ABCD1 - BCL10	1009	470	1597	ABCD1 - BCL10	1016	2440	2411
ABCG1 - BCL10	1613	310	1115	ABCG1 - BCL10	1146	676	16
ABCG2 - BCL10	361	676	2020	ABCG2 - BCL10	1263	1421	218

Table 10: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between ABC and BCL family members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

BCL w.r.t ABC

ABC-C5	BCL2L1
ABC-B11/C5/C13/D1	BCL2L2
ABC-B11/C5/C13/D1/G1	BCL2L13
ABC-D1/G1	BCL3
ABC-B11	BCL6
ABC-B11	BCL10

ABC w.r.t BCL

ABC-C3	BCL2L1
ABC-C5/C13	BCL2L13
ABC-C3	BCL3
ABC-C5/C13	BCL6
ABC-C5/C13/D1	BCL9L
ABC-A5/C5/C13/D1	BCL10

Table 11: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BCL and ABC family members.

225 3.1.5. CASPASE - ABC transporters cross family analysis

Hu et al. [13] observe that the loss of ABCB4 attenuates the caspase-dependent apoptosis regulating resistance to 5-Fu in colorectal cancer. Ihlefeld et al. [14] analyze whether the observed upregulation of the multidrug transporters contributed to the resistance of Sgpl1/-MEFs against chemotherapy-induced apoptosis by measuring the influence of ABC transporter inhibitors on cell viability and caspase-3 cleavage. Though recent developments, they point to the synergy between the transporters and the CASP family. In CRC cells, treated with ETC-1922159, these were found to be UP regulated. The engine allotted high numerical valued ranks to some of the 2nd order combinations between the members of the two families. Tables 12 and 13 show the rankings of ABC transporters w.r.t CASP and vice versa.

In table 12, we found **ABC-C5** to be up regulated w.r.t CASP4. These are reflected in rankings of 2495 (laplace) and 2257 (rbf) for CASP4 - ABC-C5. **ABC-C5** was up regulated w.r.t CASP5. These are reflected in rankings of 2475 (laplace) and 2234 (rbf) for CASP5 - ABC-C5. **ABC-A5/C13/D1** were up regulated w.r.t CASP7. These are reflected in rankings of 2515 (laplace) and 1742 (linear) for CASP7 - ABC-C5; 2489 (laplace) and 2418 (linear) for CASP7 - ABC-C13; and 2323 (laplace) and 2004 (linear) for CASP7 - ABC-D1. **ABC-B11/C5/D1/G1** were up regulated w.r.t CASP9. These are reflected in rankings of 2001 (linear) and 2051 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-B11; 2180 (laplace) and 2343 (linear) for CASP9 - ABC-C5; 2267 (laplace) and 2382 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-C13; 1890 (linear) and 2286 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-G1; **ABC-A5/C13** were up regulated w.r.t CASP10. These are reflected in rankings of 2292 (laplace), 2311 (linear) and 1108 (rbf) for CASP10 - ABC-A5; 2139 (laplace) and 2203 (linear) for CASP10 - ABC-C13;

In table 13, we found **ABC-C5** to be up regulated w.r.t CASP4. These are reflected in rankings of 2495 (laplace) and 2257 (rbf) for CASP4 - ABC-C5. **ABC-C5** was up regulated w.r.t CASP5. These are reflected in rankings of 2475 (laplace) and 2234 (rbf) for CASP5 - ABC-C5. **ABC-A5/C13/D1** were up regulated w.r.t CASP7. These are reflected in rankings of 2515 (laplace) and 1742 (linear) for CASP7 - ABC-C5; 2489 (laplace) and 2418 (linear) for CASP7 - ABC-C13; and 2323 (laplace) and 2004 (linear) for CASP7 - ABC-D1. **ABC-B11/C5/D1/G1** were up regulated w.r.t CASP9. These are reflected in rankings of 2001 (linear) and 2051 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-B11; 2180 (laplace) and 2343 (linear) for CASP9 - ABC-C5; 2267 (laplace) and 2382 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-C13; 1890 (linear) and 2286 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-G1; **ABC-A5/C13** were up regulated w.r.t CASP10. These are reflected in rankings of 2292 (laplace), 2311 (linear) and 1108 (rbf) for CASP10 - ABC-A5; 2139 (laplace) and 2203 (linear) for CASP10 - ABC-C13;

In table 13, we found **CASP4** to be up regulated w.r.t ABC-D1. These are reflected in rankings of 1791 (laplace) and 1954 (rbf) for CASP4 - ABC-D1. **CASP5** was up regulated w.r.t ABC-C13. These are reflected in rankings of 2286 (laplace) and 1905 (rbf) for CASP5 - ABC-C13. **CASP7** was up regulated w.r.t ABC-C5. This is reflected in rankings of 2168 (laplace), 1881 (linear) and 2016 (rbf) for CASP7 - ABC-C5. **CASP9** were up regulated w.r.t ABC-C5/C13/D1/G1. These are reflected in rankings of 2404 (laplace) and 2374 (linear) for CASP9 - ABC-A5; 2449 (laplace) and 2506 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-C13; 1858 (laplace) and 2430 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-D1; and

RANKING ABC FAMILY W.R.T CASP FAMILY							
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T CASP4				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T CASP5			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
CASP4 - ABC-A5	957	682	991	CASP5 - ABC-A5	733	1986	421
CASP4 - ABC-B11	19	727	158	CASP5 - ABC-B11	513	406	355
CASP4 - ABC-C3	1242	857	1848	CASP5 - ABC-C3	685	1694	1558
CASP4 - ABC-C5	2495	1316	2257	CASP5 - ABC-C5	2475	1038	2234
CASP4 - ABC-C13	154	1537	1206	CASP5 - ABC-C13	1660	1581	853
CASP4 - ABC-D1	1494	964	999	CASP5 - ABC-D1	354	725	1304
CASP4 - ABC-G1	1405	70	326	CASP5 - ABC-G1	298	485	382
CASP4 - ABC-G2	157	176	523	CASP5 - ABC-G2	706	846	1598
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T CASP7				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T CASP9			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
CASP7 - ABC-A5	2515	1742	25	CASP9 - ABC-A5	1125	1863	694
CASP7 - ABC-B11	1299	207	348	CASP9 - ABC-B11	729	2001	2051
CASP7 - ABC-C3	992	511	2222	CASP9 - ABC-C3	1108	1470	1465
CASP7 - ABC-C5	1232	1449	2154	CASP9 - ABC-C5	2180	2343	1732
CASP7 - ABC-C13	2489	2418	1623	CASP9 - ABC-C13	2267	1472	2382
CASP7 - ABC-D1	1544	2323	2004	CASP9 - ABC-D1	1011	1086	174
CASP7 - ABC-G1	665	382	670	CASP9 - ABC-G1	580	1890	2286
CASP7 - ABC-G2	1930	23	963	CASP9 - ABC-G2	647	2374	310
RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T CASP10				RANKING OF ABC FAMILY W.R.T CASP16			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
CASP10 - ABC-A5	2292	2311	1108	CASP16 - ABC-A5	165	408	113
CASP10 - ABC-B11	2245	1467	1182	CASP16 - ABC-B11	495	949	1417
CASP10 - ABC-C3	760	2479	923	CASP16 - ABC-C3	50	4	556
CASP10 - ABC-C5	326	485	1429	CASP16 - ABC-C5	1635	2487	1309
CASP10 - ABC-C13	2139	2203	1524	CASP16 - ABC-C13	1517	936	1236
CASP10 - ABC-D1	2210	475	1655	CASP16 - ABC-D1	1029	1210	1285
CASP10 - ABC-G1	2337	128	71	CASP16 - ABC-G1	350	756	109
CASP10 - ABC-G2	2075	1693	1306	CASP16 - ABC-G2	318	476	515

Table 12: 2nd order interaction ranking between ABC and CASP family members.

270 2342 (linear) and 2468 (rbf) for CASP9 - ABC-G1; **CASP16** were up regulated w.r.t ABC-A5. This is reflected in rankings of 2477 (linear) and 2315 (rbf) for CASP16 - ABC-A5.

275 Table 14 shows the derived influences which can be represented graphically, with the following influences - ● ABC w.r.t CASP with CASP-4 – > ABC-C5; CASP-5 – > ABC-C5; CASP-7 – > ABC-A5/C13/D1; CASP-9 – > ABC-B11/C5/D1/G1; CASP-10 – > ABC-A5/C13; and ● CASP w.r.t ABC with CASP-4 < – ABC-D1; CASP-5 < – ABC-C13; CASP-7 < – ABC-C5; CASP-9 < – ABC-C5/C13/D1/G1; CASP-16 < – ABC-A5;

RANKING CASP FAMILY W.R.T ABC FAMILY							
RANKING OF CASP4 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF CASP5 W.R.T ABC FAMILY			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
CASP4 - ABC-A5	791	586	753	CASP5 - ABC-A5	696	427	48
CASP4 - ABC-B11	462	263	427	CASP5 - ABC-B11	1470	1300	242
CASP4 - ABC-C3	1013	54	1140	CASP5 - ABC-C3	821	286	459
CASP4 - ABC-C5	2396	26	209	CASP5 - ABC-C5	2368	665	171
CASP4 - ABC-C13	1305	775	2193	CASP5 - ABC-C13	2286	739	1905
CASP4 - ABC-D1	1791	591	1954	CASP5 - ABC-D1	653	440	972
CASP4 - ABC-G1	593	99	173	CASP5 - ABC-G1	2176	446	317
CASP4 - ABC-G2	423	109	1364	CASP5 - ABC-G2	332	122	533
RANKING OF CASP7 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF CASP9 W.R.T ABC FAMILY			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
CASP7 - ABC-A5	1726	697	1874	CASP9 - ABC-A5	2404	2374	1265
CASP7 - ABC-B11	1549	189	1692	CASP9 - ABC-B11	998	1258	2046
CASP7 - ABC-C3	2331	1572	69	CASP9 - ABC-C3	1398	2358	1445
CASP7 - ABC-C5	2168	1881	2016	CASP9 - ABC-C5	1023	965	1080
CASP7 - ABC-C13	1822	865	1239	CASP9 - ABC-C13	2449	1545	2506
CASP7 - ABC-D1	111	813	2230	CASP9 - ABC-D1	1858	2430	412
CASP7 - ABC-G1	1609	983	1994	CASP9 - ABC-G1	305	2342	2468
CASP7 - ABC-G2	1094	952	102	CASP9 - ABC-G2	1868	1621	1154
RANKING OF CASP10 W.R.T ABC FAMILY				RANKING OF CASP16 W.R.T ABC FAMILY			
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
CASP10 - ABC-A5	683	1453	1437	CASP16 - ABC-A5	960	2477	2315
CASP10 - ABC-B11	1301	774	558	CASP16 - ABC-B11	402	1860	794
CASP10 - ABC-C3	369	683	1453	CASP16 - ABC-C3	171	825	23
CASP10 - ABC-C5	1823	346	761	CASP16 - ABC-C5	2467	585	258
CASP10 - ABC-C13	1320	832	868	CASP16 - ABC-C13	428	177	64
CASP10 - ABC-D1	249	1440	387	CASP16 - ABC-D1	651	153	2010
CASP10 - ABC-G1	1687	1232	156	CASP16 - ABC-G1	2398	421	1120
CASP10 - ABC-G2	1151	651	464	CASP16 - ABC-G2	1193	734	479

Table 13: 2nd order interaction ranking between CASP and ABC family members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

ABC w.r.t CASP

CASP-4	ABC-C5
CASP-5	ABC-C5
CASP-7	ABC-A5/C13/D1
CASP-9	ABC-B11/C5/D1/G1
CASP-10	ABC-A5/C13

CASP w.r.t ABC

CASP-4	ABC-D1
CASP-5	ABC-C13
CASP-7	ABC-C5
CASP-9	ABC-C5/C13/D1/G1
CASP-16	ABC-A5

Table 14: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between BCL and ABC family members.

Conclusion

280 Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic ABC transporter 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a search engine. Later, two way cross family analysis between components of these combinations were conducted. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations that might be prevalent in CRC cells after treatment with ETC-1922159 drug.
285 The two-way cross family analysis also assists in deriving influences between components which serve as hypotheses for further tests. If found true, it paves way for biologists/oncologists to further investigate and understand the mechanism behind the synergy through wet experiments.

Conflict of interest

290 There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

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